

A NOVEL PROCESSING TECHNIQUE FOR MANUFACTURING OF PP COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH NANOPARTICLES

W. H. Ruan¹, M Q Zhang¹, M H Wang¹, M. Z Rong¹, T. Bárány², T. Czigány²

¹Materials Science Institute, Zhongshan University

²Department of Polymer Engineering, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest, Hungary

Zhongshan University, Guangzhou, P. R. China, 510275

cesrwh@mail.sysu.edu.cn y

SUMMARY

A new technique, that the nanoparticles filled Polypropylene(PP) sheets were stretched under a temperature slightly lower than the melt point of PP, then the sheets were film-stacked with random PP copolymer, was developed in this work. The resultant nanocomposites are much stronger and stiffer than the unfilled PP.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Polypropylene, Film-stacking, Processing conditions

INTRODUCTION

Polymer based nanocomposites, in which inorganic nanoparticles are dispersed in organic polymer matrices, represent a new class of materials due to their unique properties resulting from the nano-scale microstructure. It has been recognized that homogeneous dispersion of nanoparticles and enhancement of nanoparticles/matrix interfacial interaction are critical for giving scope to nanoparticles. However, nanoparticles tend to agglomerate during blending with polymer matrix. Surface treatment of nanoparticles is necessary to decrease the surface energy of nanoparticles. Graft polymerization onto nanoparticles proves to be an effective method to increase hydrophobicity of the particles, and to bring about tunable interfacial interaction in nanocomposites because of entanglement between molecular chains of grafting polymer and that of polymer matrix [1]. Our early investigation revealed that when tension is applied, the grafted nanoparticle agglomerates in composites could be extended and broken up along the tensile direction, thus the dispersion of nanoparticles can be improved [2]. The well dispersed nanoparticles could induce the structure change of polymer matrix, and help the matrix to keep the oriented structure. The molecular orientation greatly contributes to mechanical properties improvement of polymer [3]. On the basis of the above considerations, a new route that combining unidirectional drawing of nanoparticles filled polymer with hot consolidation technique for composites was developed in our laboratory. Because processing conditions of hot consolidation, such as molding temperature, holding pressure and holding temperature, can limit the application of such materials and so must be understood.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fumed SiO₂ (Aerosil 200, average diameter = 12nm, specific surface area = 200m²/g) produced by Degussa Co., Germany was chosen as filler. Isotactic polypropylene (PP) (H1500®, melting flow index = 11.5g/10min, ASTM D1238) supplied by Hyundai Petroleum Chemical Co., Korea. Random PP copolymer (Tipplen 959A, melting flow index =45.0g/10min) supplied by TVK, Hungary. The nanoparticles were preheated at 140°C under vacuum for 5h. Then the mixture of monomer (butyl acrylate) and the nanoparticles and a certain amount of solvent was irradiated by ⁶⁰Co γ -ray in air at a dose rate of 8Mrad. The resultant, poly (butyl acrylate) (PBA) grafted nano- SiO₂ (SiO₂-g-PBA) with a percent grafting of 3.35%, was used for the subsequent composites manufacturing. Untreated or treated nano-silica was melt compounded with PP1500 at 180°C in the mixer of Haake Rheocord 300p torque rheometer, respectively. The content of nano-silica in all the composites is 1.36vol%. The sheets of SiO₂ /PP was produced by hot compression, and then the sheets were hot drawn under a temperature slight lower than the melt point of PP(150 °C) at a constant velocity to produce stretched sheets(marked as A). Film with a thickness of 50 μ m was made from the random PP copolymer by blowing(marked as B). Finally, the stretched tapes were film-stacked with copolymer films by a special designed mold and were hot pressed at different processing temperature (T=150-175°C), holding pressure (2.0-5.0MPa) and holding time(5-15min). The flow diagram of processing technique is shown in Fig.1. Structure and orientation of the PP crystals in the stretched tapes were studied by a Rigaku D/MAX 2200 VPC wide angle X-ray diffractometer (WAXD) with Cu K α radiation. The scanning range of Bragg 2 θ angle is from 5 to 35° with a scanning rate of 4°/min. The ratio of the intensity of the (110) reflection (2 θ =14.4°), I (110), to the intensity of the (040) reflection (2 θ =16.3°), I (040), was calculated to evaluate the orientation degree of the a-axis of PP crystal of stretched sheets [4]. Crystallinity and melting behaviors of PP and its nanocomposites were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on a TA MDSC2910 apparatus at a heating rate of 10oC/min.. Tensile properties of the nanocomposites were determined with a Honsefield 10K-S universal tester at a crosshead speed of 50mm min⁻¹ according to ASTM D638-98.

Fig. 1 Flow diagram of composite processing technique

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In consideration of processing technique, to maintain the high degree of molecular alignment of stretched sheets and so attain the high mechanical properties, chosen copolymer are critical. From DSC curve of PP and PP copolymer(Fig.2), we can see that melting temperature of PP copolymer is 15°C lower than PP homopolymer. Thus appropriate processing windows could be found.

Fig.2 DSC curve of PP homopolymer and PP copolymer

Effects of Processing Conditions of Hot Consolidation

Fig 3 Tensile properties of the self-reinforced nanocomposites as a function of the processing temperature (holding pressure=2.3MPa, holding time=10min)

From curves of tensile properties of the hot-compacted nanocomposites as a function of the molding temperature(Fig.3), we can see that at temperature of 155-160°C, the copolymer film molten while the PP reinforcement with oriented structure do not melt and hence keep their properties, the higher tensile strength could be acquired. With the

temperature increase exceed the melting temperature of PP homopolymer, the molecular relaxation of oriented stretched sheets would cause tensile properties to dramatically decrease. And curves of tensile properties of the nanocomposites as a function of the holding pressure (Fig.4) show that suitable pressure (2.0-2.5MPa) is enough for consolidation of composites. Lower pressure provides poor bonding between copolymer and stretched sheets, on the other hand, higher pressure would pile out molten copolymer from composites and weaken welding capacity. Holding time has little effect on tensile strength. The optimum processing conditions for hot consolidation of nanoparticles filled PP composites are processing temperature of 155-160 °C , holding pressure of 20.-25MPa, holding time of 5-10min.

Fig 4 Tensile properties of the self-reinforced nanocomposites as a function of the holding pressure (processing temperature=155, holding time=10min)

Tensile Properties of Nanocomposites

Fig 5 The typical stress-strain curves of PP and its nanocomposites

Typical tensile stress-strain curves of PP and nanoparticles filled unidirectional composites are shown in Fig.5. It can be seen that dramatically improved tensile properties can be achieved via above route. The tensile properties of hot compacted unidirectional composites are much higher than common compounded samples. The addition of nanoparticles further improved the tensile properties of composites, and as viewed from the failure strain, toughness of PP composites also improved at the same time.

Orientation of PP crystals

To study the reason why the addition of grafted nanoparticles could improve the mechanical properties of PP composites, the stretched sheets used as reinforcement were investigated first. Could the aligned nanoparticle agglomerates induce the orientation of PP polymer? Table 1 lists the relative intensity $I(110)/I(040)$ of the stretched sheets measured by wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) to evaluate the degree of crystal orientation of PP. It is unexpected to see that crystalline orientation of PP even slight decrease when nanoparticles are added. As PP is a semi-crystalline polymer, we should inquire about the orientation of amorphous part, but we could not find effective method up to now.

Table 1 Crystal orientation of stretched sheets of PP and its composites characterized by relative WAXD intensity.

Materials	Relative Intensity(110) [a.u.]	Relative Intensity(040) [a.u.]	$I(110)/I(040)$
PP-A(stretched)	100	71.3	1.40
SiO ₂ /PP-A (stretched)	100	82	1.22
SiO ₂ -g-PBA/PP-A (stretched)	100	80.6	1.24

Crystallization and Melting Characteristics of PP Composites

Considering that PP is a semicrystalline polymer, it should be understood whether the crystallization characteristics of the hot compacted composites is affected by the incorporation of nanoparticles. Table 2 collects the DSC studies of non-isothermal crystallization and melting data of the related materials. The data show that melting point of PP is nearly not affected by the nano-silica; it means that no transition of crystal form occurs. On the other hand, supercooling temperature (ΔT) of the PP decreases with the addition of nanoparticles, indicating that crystallization of the nanocomposites becomes easier owing to the nucleation effect of the nanoparticles. The grafted nano-silica filled composites have lower ΔT but higher crystallinity than other composites. These might contribute to the performance improvement of resultant composites.

Table 2 Non-isothermal crystallization and melting characteristics of PP composites

Materials	T_m [°C]	T_c [°C]	ΔT [°C]	X_c [%]
PP copolymer	147.5	118.1	29.4	38.9
PP	163.0	112.9	50.1	46.7
SiO ₂ /PP	162.3	115.2	47.1	46.6
SiO ₂ -g-PBA/PP	161.3	117.0	44.3	38.7
PP-SRC	160.7	119.6	49.9	52.0
SiO ₂ /PP-SRC	162.6	119.0	44.9	49.9
SiO ₂ -g-PBA/PP-SRC	162.9	122.0	40.9	60.3

CONCLUSION

From the above analysis, it is clear that the addition of nanoparticles can improve mechanical properties of unidirectional PP composites. The proposed methods of drawing aided dispersion of nanoparticles might also be applicable to the preparation of other nanoparticles/polymer composites. A comprehensive understanding of the underlying parameters involved in this approach and a further exploration of reinforcing mechanism would facilitate manufacturing polymer nanocomposites with balanced performance by existing melt compounding methods.

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